

Title: Analyzing Even Numbers as Ordered Pairs of Primes

Abstract: This study presents a method to demonstrate that the sum of two prime numbers can generate all even numbers greater than 2. By arranging prime numbers in ascending order, forming ordered pairs based on their positions, and summing them, a systematic pattern emerges. Each prime number, indexed as n , generates n ordered pairs, where the first pair for each value of n always consists of the same prime number itself. This approach showcases the versatility of prime numbers in generating even numbers and offers a structured framework for understanding their arithmetic properties. Through this exploration, fundamental insights into the distribution of even numbers as sums of primes are revealed.

Introduction:

Prime numbers, a fundamental concept in number theory, have fascinated mathematicians for centuries due to their unique properties and significant implications. The study of prime numbers encompasses a wide range of topics, ranging from their distribution and properties to their applications in cryptography and computing. However, one particularly fascinating aspect of prime numbers is their role in generating “**even numbers greater than 2 through their summation**”. This phenomenon has gained considerable attention in mathematical research, as it shows the inherent structure and interconnectedness of prime numbers within the domain of even integers.

Existing research in this area has primarily focused on establishing theorems and conjectures related to prime numbers and their additive properties. Early investigations by mathematicians such as **Euler** and **Goldbach** laid the groundwork for understanding the relationship between prime numbers and even integers. However, despite the research on prime numbers, there remains a need for a systematic exploration of their role in producing even numbers greater than 2 through pairing and summation.

In this study, we aim to address this gap by presenting a structured approach to examining the additive properties of prime numbers and their ability to yield even integers greater than 2. By defining a specific research problem centered around prime number summation and positioning our approach within the context of existing research, we aim to contribute novel findings to the field of number theory.

Methodology:

It involves systematically pairing prime numbers to demonstrate their ability to yield all even numbers greater than 2 as sums.

- Beginning with the smallest prime, 2, the process sorts prime numbers in ascending order, denoted as $P_n = 2, 3, 5, 7$, and so forth, where P_n represents the prime number of the n th position. Since they are sorted in ascending order, so $P_1=2, P_2=3, P_3=5$ and so on.
- For each subsequent value of n , representing the position of the prime number in the ascending sequence, **ordered pairs** are formed.
- The first ordered pair in each set always consists of the same prime number itself, which means (P_n, P_n) , representing the even number obtained when adding the elements of that certain ordered pair.
- As n increases, additional ordered pairs are generated, each consisting of the n th prime paired with subsequent primes. For instance, when $n = 2$, the pairs (P_n, P_n) and (P_n, P_{n+1}) are formed, where P_{n+1} represents the next prime after P_n .
- This process continues iteratively and each prime number indexed as ' n ' generates ' n ' ordered pairs.
- For example:

$$n = 1: (P_n, P_n) = (P_1, P_1) = (2, 2)$$

$$n = 2: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}) = (3, 3), (3, 5)$$

$$n = 3: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}) = (5, 5), (5, 7), (5, 11)$$

$$n = 4: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), (P_n, P_{n+3}) = (7, 7), (7, 11), (7, 13), (7, 17)$$

$$n = 5: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), (P_n, P_{n+3}), (P_n, P_{n+4}) = (11, 11), (11, 13), (11, 17), (11, 19), (11, 23)$$

$$n = 6: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), (P_n, P_{n+3}), (P_n, P_{n+4}), (P_n, P_{n+5}) = (13, 13), (13, 17), (13, 19), (13, 23), (13, 29), (13, 31)$$

$$n = 7: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), (P_n, P_{n+3}), (P_n, P_{n+4}), (P_n, P_{n+5}), (P_n, P_{n+6}) = (17, 17), (17, 19), (17, 23), (17, 29), (17, 31), (17, 37), (17, 41)$$

$$n = 8: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), (P_n, P_{n+3}), (P_n, P_{n+4}), (P_n, P_{n+5}), (P_n, P_{n+6}), (P_n, P_{n+7}) = (19, 19), (19, 23), (19, 29), (19, 31), (19, 37), (19, 41), (19, 43), (19, 47)$$

$$n = 9: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), (P_n, P_{n+3}), (P_n, P_{n+4}), (P_n, P_{n+5}), (P_n, P_{n+6}), (P_n, P_{n+7}), (P_n, P_{n+8}) = (23, 23), (23, 29), (23, 31), (23, 37), (23, 41), (23, 43), (23, 47), (23, 53), (23, 59)$$

$n = 10: (P_n, P_n), (P_n, P_{n+1}), (P_n, P_{n+2}), = (29, 29), (29, 31), (29, 37), (29, 41), (29, 43), (29, 47),$
 $(P_n, P_{n+3}), (P_n, P_{n+4}), (P_n, P_{n+5}), (29, 53), (29, 59), (29, 61), (29, 67)$
 $(P_n, P_{n+6}), (P_n, P_{n+7}), (P_n, P_{n+8}),$
 (P_n, P_{n+9})

This pairing method captures the core idea of prime number addition, showing that when you add any prime number to itself (P_n, P_n), you always get an **even number greater than 2**. Furthermore, the subsequent pairs like (P_n, P_{n+1}) highlight **prime numbers** can be combined to create a wide range of **even numbers**. Essentially, each ordered pair in this framework represents a distinct prime number duo whose sum is always an even number greater than 2.

$n = 1: (2, 2)$	$\rightarrow 4$
$n = 2: (3, 3), (3, 5)$	$\rightarrow 6, 8$
$n = 3: (5, 5), (5, 7), (5, 11)$	$\rightarrow 10, 12, 16$
$n = 4: (7, 7), (7, 11), (7, 13), (7, 17)$	$\rightarrow 14, 18, 20, 24$
$n = 5: (11, 11), (11, 13), (11, 17), (11, 19), (11, 23)$	$\rightarrow 22, 24, 28, 30, 34$
$n = 6: (13, 13), (13, 17), (13, 19), (13, 23), (13, 29),$ $(13, 31)$	$\rightarrow 26, 30, 32, 36, 42, 44$
$n = 7: (17, 17), (17, 19), (17, 23), (17, 29), (17, 31),$ $(17, 37), (17, 41)$	$\rightarrow 34, 36, 40, 46, 48, 54, 58$
$n = 8: (19, 19), (19, 23), (19, 29), (19, 31), (19, 37),$ $(19, 41), (19, 43), (19, 47)$	$\rightarrow 38, 42, 48, 50, 56, 60, 62, 66$
$n = 9: (23, 23), (23, 29), (23, 31), (23, 37), (23, 41),$ $(23, 43), (23, 47), (23, 53), (23, 59)$	$\rightarrow 46, 52, 54, 60, 64, 66, 70, 76, 82$
$n = 10: (29, 29), (29, 31), (29, 37), (29, 41), (29, 43),$ $(29, 47), (29, 53), (29, 59), (29, 61), (29, 67)$	$\rightarrow 58, 60, 66, 70, 72, 76, 82, 88, 90,$ 96
$n = 11: (31, 31), (31, 37), (31, 41), (31, 43), (31, 47),$ $(31, 53), (31, 59), (31, 61), (31, 67), (31, 71),$ $(31, 73)$	$\rightarrow 62, 68, 72, 74, 78, 84, 90, 92, 98,$ $102, 104$
$n = 12: (37, 37), (37, 41), (37, 43), (37, 47), (37, 53),$ $(37, 59), (37, 61), (37, 67), (37, 71), (37, 73),$ $(37, 79), (37, 83)$	$\rightarrow 74, 78, 80, 84, 90, 96, 98, 104,$ $108, 110, 116, 120$

n = 13: (41,41), (41,43), (41,47), (41,53), (41,59), (41,61), (41,67), (41,71), (41,73), (41,79), (41,83), (41,89), (41,97)	→ 82, 84, 88, 94, 100, 102, 108, 112, 114, 120, 124, 130, 138
n = 14: (43,43), (43,47), (43,53), (43,59), (43,61), (43,67), (43,71), (43,73), (43,79), (43,83), (43,89), (43,97), (43,101), (43,103)	→ 86, 90, 96, 102, 104, 110, 114, 116, 122, 126, 132, 140, 144, 146
n = 15: (47,47), (47,53), (47,59), (47,61), (47,67), (47,71), (47,73), (47,79), (47,83), (47,89), (47,97), (47,101), (47,103), (47,107), (47,109)	→ 94, 100, 106, 108, 114, 118, 120, 126, 130, 136, 144, 148, 150, 154, 156

and so on.

Even numbers which are in **Red** color, indicates that these even numbers are already discovered in the previous values of **n**.

Conclusion:

This investigation sheds light on the remarkable capacity of prime numbers to generate **all even integers greater than 2** through a methodical process of pairing and summation. Employing a structured approach involving the **sorting** of prime numbers in ascending order and the formation of **ordered pairs** based on their positional values, a framework emerges, elucidating the intrinsic association between prime numbers and the set of even numbers. This scholarly inquiry contributes significantly to the deepening of our understanding concerning the additive properties inherent in prime numbers, thereby underscoring their fundamental role in shaping the domain of even integers beyond the threshold of 2.

References:

1. Goldbach's conjecture, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goldbach's_conjecture
2. Sums of powers of primes, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11139-016-9847-4>
3. Prime numbers, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prime_number
4. Goldbach's conjecture, <https://www.britannica.com/science/Goldbach-conjecture>
5. Prime number and their analysis, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339642995_Prime_numbers_and_their_analysis
6. Properties of Prime numbers, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4613-0015-1_5